

Question Guide for Public V.4

Introduction

Thank you so much for coming to the interview! As I mentioned, this interview is a part of a big research project called 'Fair MusE' that aims to better our common understanding of how music streaming platforms shape music listening today - e.g., how their algorithms and recommendations, as well as curated playlists affect how we listen to music.

The purpose of the interview, and why we want to speak to users like you, is that we really want to get a better understanding of how users experience the streaming services. We also want to get your perspectives on how - and if - fairness is a relevant benchmark for judging the success of streaming services.

I also want to just clarify that what you share with me **will be anonymised**, so that it cannot be referred back to you. The findings, and thus snippets from this interview might be shared in an open-source article on the topic - as well as on our website as quotes. But you are always open to writing to us if you want us to remove or take down any statements you made. Is that okay with you?

Background

First off, I would like to ask a few initial questions - just to get a little background on you: name, age, gender, profession, country of residence, and native language.

Listening Habits

Now, I would like to ask you a few basic questions about your music listening habits.

- First of all, what role would you say music plays in your everyday life?
- How often do you listen to music?
- How do you typically listen to music? (e.g., via streaming, CDs, vinyl, live at concerts.)
 - a. Do you also own music, e.g. albums, vinyl records, etc.?
 - i. If yes, do you feel it gives you a different experience than streaming? If so, in what way?
- When do you listen to music?
 - a. What situations make you turn on the music? - and why?
 - b. What does music give you in the respective situations? What's the purpose of listening for you?

- What languages do you listen to?
 - a. Do you ever listen to non-English-speaking music?
 - b. Do you ever listen to music from other European countries?

For interviewees above 35/40: Do you remember how you used to listen to music before the streaming services started appearing in 2005?

- Do you feel your way of listening to music has changed because of this?

- In what ways?

Perception of the platform and recommendations

- Why did you choose X platform?
 - Why did you choose this one compared to X or X?
 - Have you tried the other platforms?
 - Are you a paying user or?
 - Have you ever considered changing platforms?
- Do you know the recommendation systems that this/these platform(s) use to suggest music to you? / Are you familiar with the concept of music recommendation systems?
 - Have you noticed what music is recommended to you? E.g. what type of music is presented at your interface when you open up the ‘browse’ site.
 - If yes, what kind of music?
 - And are you satisfied with the recommendations? Do you think they enhance your listening experience?
 - Is getting good recommendations an important feature for you when choosing your platform?
- Would you prefer that the recommendation systems give you more of what you already like or would you like them to challenge you to discover new music?
 - E.g. Would you like the algorithm to introduce you to more music from other countries or other genres? Or do you actually enjoy just getting what you already know?
- **For musicians:** Do you think about the recommendation systems as a musician? Does it affect your creative process?
- Do you listen to the playlists that are made by the platform or by other users?
 - Do you think about who builds your playlists? Do you find it transparent?
 - If so, why? And how satisfied are you with the playlists you find?
 - Do you find any differences between the ones made by the platform and the ones by users? Do you have a preference?
- 1. Do you discover new music via streaming?
 - Outside of streaming, where do you discover new music?

Perception of what role platforms should play in terms of fairness

As mentioned before, besides being interested in understanding the listening habits of users, we are also curious to hear from you what role you think music streaming platforms play/should play when it comes to securing fairness and diversity within the industry.

- First of all - I want to ask you, what do you think of when I say fairness? What does it mean to you?

- Is fairness something you think about when you buy something normally - e.g. when grocery shopping or buying new clothes? If yes/no, why?
- Have you ever thought of the aspect of fairness relating to music streaming services? Whether or not it's fair to e.g. artists?
- Is it important to you that the streaming service you use is fair?
 - If yes, what forms of fairness have been important to you?
 - If not, why do you think that is? Is fairness an irrelevant question when it comes to music?
- Do you think about how your way of consuming music affects artists?
 - Whose responsibility is it to secure fairness? Yours or the platform? Or someone else's?
- Do you think streaming platforms have a responsibility to ensure diversity in music? If yes, in what ways?
 - Is it okay that the algorithms boost the hits? Or do they have a role in protecting or promoting artists that aren't that popular (yet)?
 - Is it important to ensure diversity in music at all?
- Do you think it's transparent about how the algorithms work? Do you think that's important?

Maybe add: Do you think fairness indicators could be a way to regulate the platforms?

I. Conclusion

- If you were the boss of Spotify, what would you change? What would you keep?
- Is there anything you would like to share, add or reflect on based on our conversation?

Thank you for participating in the interview!

(If they haven't uploaded data, remind them and ask about if we can help or they had any problems in the process.)